

INTENSIFICATION OF THE STRUGGLE AGAINST RELIGIOUS FANATICISM, IGNORANCE AND INTERNATIONAL TERRORISM AS AN URGENT TASK OF OUR TIME

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Abstract. *The article examines religious fanaticism, social ignorance and international terrorism as interrelated threats to public security and sustainable development of modern society. Social, educational and ideological factors of radicalization are analyzed, the role of distorted religious consciousness and the deficit of critical thinking in the formation of extremist attitudes is revealed. terrorism and the need for a comprehensive approach to its prevention.*

Keywords: *religious fanaticism, ignorance, international terrorism, radicalization, extremism, prevention, public safety.*

Introduction. In the current conditions of globalization and rapid information exchange, modern society faces qualitatively new security challenges. Religious fanaticism, social ignorance and international terrorism are becoming stable and interrelated, going beyond the boundaries of individual states and affecting the foundations of the international legal order. humanitarian values.

Religious fanaticism is often the ideological basis of extremist movements, while ignorance and low levels of education create a fertile environment for the spread of radical ideas. Using these conditions, international terrorism is transforming into a global threat that requires systematic scientific comprehension.

The purpose of the study is to identify the key factors in the formation of religious fanaticism, social ignorance and international terrorism, as well as to substantiate the priority areas for their prevention in modern conditions.

Review of the studied scientific literature. Modern scientific research emphasizes that religious fanaticism is formed as a result of a distorted interpretation of religious norms and values, as well as their use for political and extremist purposes. According to a number of authors, radical movements actively exploit religious identity, replacing spiritual meanings with the ideology of violence [1].

In the reports of international organizations, including the UN and UNESCO, special attention is paid to the role of education and information policy in the prevention of extremism. It is noted that the low level of legal and cultural literacy increases the vulnerability of society to radical propaganda, especially among young people [2].

Studies on international terrorism focus on its transnational nature, the use of digital technologies and network structures [3]. Modern terrorism is characterized by a high degree of adaptability and the ability to integrate into global processes, which significantly complicates countering these threats.

Research methodology. In the course of the study, the author applies the methods of theoretical analysis of scientific publications, comparative study of international experience in countering extremism and terrorism, as well as the logical and analytical method. The empirical basis of the study consists of official reports of international organizations, regulatory documents

and the results of expert assessments. effective ways to prevent religious fanaticism, ignorance and international terrorism.

Main part. A fan is an individual characterized by uncritical and excessive adherence to certain religious, ideological or political beliefs, accompanied by intolerance of alternative views and a willingness to justify radical forms of behavior.

Fanaticism is a socio-psychological and ideological phenomenon expressed in the absolutization of individual ideas or dogmas, their elevation to the rank of unconditional truth and the rejection of the pluralism of opinions. In the religious context, fanaticism manifests itself in the distorted interpretation of beliefs, the loss of humanistic values, and the use of religion as a tool to justify violence and extremist activity, in particular:

1. Distorted religious interpretation, in which individual dogmas are taken out of context and used to justify radical ideas.
2. Low level of religious and secular education, which hinders the formation of critical thinking and conscious understanding of religious values.
3. Social marginalization and a sense of injustice, which contribute to the search for simple answers to complex social and personal problems.
4. Manipulative influence of radical leaders and propagandists who use religious rhetoric to mobilize supporters.
5. Identity crisis, especially characteristic of young people in search of meaning, belonging and social significance.
6. The information impact of extremist resources distributed through digital platforms and social networks.

Social ignorance is a combination of insufficient knowledge in the field of law, culture, history and socio-political processes, as well as a lack of skills for critical comprehension of information. It is expressed in the inability of individuals and social groups to adequately perceive social reality, which increases their vulnerability to manipulative and extremist influence.

Radicalization is a multi-stage process of the formation of extreme ideological attitudes, accompanied by an increase in intolerance of alternative views, a rejection of dialogue and, in some cases, justification or use of violence. Social ignorance acts as a catalyst for radicalization, facilitating the spread of extremist ideas in society, especially among young people.

Ignorance is one of the key factors contributing to the spread of extremist ideas. These are: Firstly, the insufficient level of education, limited access to reliable information and poor development of critical thinking create conditions for the manipulation of public consciousness. A particularly vulnerable category is young people who are in search of social identity and life guidelines.

Secondly, a significant role is played by the deficit of critical thinking skills, expressed in the inability to analyze sources of information, distinguish facts from interpretations and identify the manipulative nature of messages. In conditions of information overload, this leads to an uncritical perception of radical ideas and conspiracy theories.

Third, an important factor is limited access to reliable and high-quality information, especially in socially vulnerable groups and remote regions. Insufficient development of media literacy contributes to the spread of disinformation, pseudoscientific and extremist materials actively used by radical structures.

Fourth, socio-economic instability, unemployment, poverty and social inequality create a sense of frustration, injustice and alienation from society. In such conditions, radical ideologies are often perceived as a means of self-realization, the search for meaning, and the explanation of personal failures.

Fifth, the weakening of traditional institutions of socialization—the family, the education system, and cultural and public organizations—reduces the effectiveness of the transmission of social norms, values, and models of constructive behavior. This is especially dangerous for young people who are in the process of forming a worldview and social identity.

Therefore, taken together, these factors create a favorable environment for the formation of social ignorance, which, in turn, significantly increases the risk of radicalization and involvement of individuals in extremist and terrorist activities.

International terrorism is a form of organized violent activity carried out by transnational terrorist groups with the aim of destabilizing international and national security, exerting political, ideological or religious pressure on states and civil society, as well as intimidating the population. Unlike domestic terrorism, international terrorism goes beyond national borders, affecting the interests of the population at once several states and international organizations.

In the context of globalization, international terrorism is acquiring new features associated with the intensification of cross-border processes, the development of information and communication technologies, the growth of population mobility and the interdependence of States. Globalization contributes to the formation of terrorist networks that are able to quickly adapt to changing conditions, use digital platforms for propaganda and recruitment, and coordinate actions at the international level. This is:

First, political instability and armed conflict are a key factor, especially in regions with weak governance. Military crises, civil wars and the destruction of state institutions create a favorable environment for the activities of terrorist organizations and their transnational spread.

Second, ideological and religious radicalization plays a significant role, in which extremist interpretations of ideologies are used to justify violence and attract supporters from different countries. Terrorist organizations actively exploit issues of identity, social injustice, and cultural contradictions.

Third, the globalization of the information space is an important factor. The development of the Internet and social networks allows terrorist organizations to carry out propaganda, recruitment, and coordination of actions at the international level with minimal costs and a high level of anonymity.

Fourth, socio-economic inequality and marginalization of the population contribute to the formation of a fertile ground for radicalization. Unemployment, poverty, lack of social mobility and prospects increase the sense of alienation and protest sentiments, which are used by terrorist ideologues.

Fifthly, the lack of effective international cooperation, including incoherence among States, differences in legal systems and limited exchange of operational information, has a significant impact. This allows terrorist organizations to exploit gaps in international security.

Taken together, these factors determine the stability of international terrorism, its ability to adapt to the conditions of globalization and pose one of the most serious threats to modern world security.

Discussion. Religious fanaticism, social ignorance and international terrorism form an interrelated and self-reproducing system of threats. Social ignorance creates a fertile ground for a distorted perception of religious and ideological ideas, reducing the ability of the individual to critically comprehend information. In turn, it uses the results of these processes, transforming local forms of radicalism into transnational networks of violence, which increases the destabilizing impact on society and international security. Consequently, each of these phenomena not only strengthens the other, but also contributes to its further spread. The report of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) "*Preventing Violent Extremism*

through Education: A Guide for Policy-Makers" emphasizes that the key areas for preventing radicalization are the development of critical thinking, improving the quality of education, creating a culture of dialogue and tolerance, as well as strengthening the social integration of young people [4]. Supporting this approach, it should be noted that in the work of **Bruce Hoffman's "Inside Terrorism"** emphasizes the need to combine educational, legal and socio-cultural measures to reduce the influence of radical ideology and prevent terrorist manifestations [5].

Conclusions and proposals. Thus, in our opinion, we can draw the following conclusions:

1) Religious fanaticism is formed in conditions of distorted religious consciousness and social isolation;

2) Social ignorance significantly increases susceptibility to extremist propaganda;

3) International terrorism uses the processes of globalization and digitalization;

4) Effective counteraction is possible only with an integrated and systematic approach.

In modern conditions, the priority areas for the prevention of religious fanaticism, social ignorance and international terrorism are measures aimed at eliminating their root causes and factors of spread.

First of all, it is of key importance to strengthen the role of education, focused not only on the transfer of knowledge, but also on the formation of critical thinking, legal culture and resistance to manipulative ideologies. Educational programs should contribute to the development of skills in information analysis, understanding of the diversity of cultures and worldviews, as well as the development of respect for human rights and freedoms. International experience shows that education is one of the most effective tools for preventing radicalization, especially among young people [6]. At the same time, an important area is the development of intercultural and interfaith dialogue aimed at reducing the level of social tension and preventing conflicts based on religious and ideological differences. Support for dialogue platforms, public initiatives and cultural programs contributes to the formation of tolerance and mutual understanding in society.

In addition, enhanced international cooperation, including the exchange of information, coordination of law enforcement efforts and the joint development of strategies to combat transnational terrorist threats, is a prerequisite for effective counteraction. A comprehensive combination of preventive, educational and legal measures makes it possible not only to reduce the level of terrorist activity, but also to ensure the long-term sustainability of public and international security, international cooperation in the field of prevention of extremism and terrorism.

Therefore, in particular: Education is one of the key and most effective tools for the prevention of extremism and terrorism in modern conditions. It is aimed not only at the transfer of knowledge, but also at the formation of stable value orientations, critical thinking and the ability to resist manipulative ideologies. Of particular importance is the development of a legal and civil culture that makes it possible to understand social responsibility, respect human rights and freedoms, as well as understand the consequences of extremist activity. International studies emphasize that the systematic implementation of educational programs focused on tolerance, dialogue and media literacy significantly reduces the risk of radicalization of young people and increases society's resistance to extremist propaganda [7].

The development of intercultural and interfaith dialogue is an important area of prevention of radicalization and extremism, as it helps to reduce social tension and create an atmosphere of mutual respect in society. Dialogue between different cultures, religions and ethnic groups can overcome stereotypes, prevent identity conflicts and strengthen social cohesion. Support for cultural initiatives, educational projects and public platforms for dialogue contributes to the

formation of tolerance and mutual understanding, which significantly weakens the influence of radical ideologies and reduces the likelihood of involving citizens in extremist activities.

Expanding international cooperation is a prerequisite for effectively countering extremism and international terrorism in the context of globalization. The transnational nature of modern terrorist threats requires the coordination of efforts of states, international organizations and law enforcement agencies. The exchange of information, the harmonization of legal mechanisms, joint prevention programmes and international initiatives make it possible to identify threats in a timely manner and prevent the spread of radical networks. United Nations documents emphasize that sustainable results in the fight against extremism are achieved through a combination of national measures and active international cooperation [8].

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